

Assessing the Role of Social Media in Promoting the *Obidient* Movement During the 2023 Presidential Election in Nigeria

Igwe Kingsley Udochukwu

Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-3426-1494>

*Nwambam Maduka

Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9936-5354>

Department of Mass Communication, Mountain Top University, Km 12, Lagos-Ibadan Expressway, Prayer City, Ogun State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author email: mnwambam@mtu.edu.ng

Background: *The Obidient* movement refers to the political movement that emerged as a build-up to the 2023 presidential election to support the presidential ambition of Mr Peter Obi, the candidate of the Labour Party in the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

Objective: This study sought to determine the role of social media in supporting the *Obidient* political movement during Nigeria's 2023 presidential election

Methodology: The researchers used a descriptive survey as the design of the study. The sample size was 385 self-confessed *Obidient* members who were also social media users. The respondent-driven chain referral sampling was used in the study. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, and the results were presented in two tables and one chart.

Results: Several events triggered the *Obidient* political movement. They include the desire for a Nigerian president of Igbo extraction, Mr Obi's promises, Obi's defection from the PDP as a result of perceived bad treatment, the Muslim/Muslim ticket of the APC, federal government's handling of the ENDSAR protests, prolonged 2022 ASUU strike, the emergence of Alhaji Atiku Abubakar, another Northerner as a PDP presidential candidate, concerns about the health of the APC presidential candidate and endorsement of Mr Obi by some groups and individuals. The result on the ways social media platforms were used to promote the *Obidient* movement showed that this included engagement with Mr Obi's social media posts, posting of Mr Obi's activities on social media, trying to convince other people through social media why Mr Obi was the best, sharing Mr Obi's previous records on social media, sharing information on the weaknesses of other candidates, Pointing out instances of bad governance in Nigeria and creation of group social media platforms. Finally, the result revealed that the majority of the respondents agreed that social media was used to a large extent to organise physical events for the political movement.

Conclusion: Social media platforms were significantly used to promote the *Obidient* political movement in Nigeria, triggering online and offline activities.

Unique contribution: This study has provided empirical data showing the role of social media in promoting political movements in developing democracies.

Key Recommendation: Future researchers should investigate the contributing role of age and gender in using social media for political movements.

Keywords: social media, political movement, *Obidient* movement, presidential election;

Introduction

What is known as the *Obi-dient* movement became part of Nigeria's political lexicon during the 2023 presidential election. As a buildup to the election, the former Governor of Anambra State, Mr Peter Obi, defected from the People's Democratic Party (PDP) to the Labour Party (LP). Mr Obi defected from the PDP after it became apparent to him that he would not get the party's Presidential ticket. He found refuge in the Labour Party and quickly became its candidate for president. His messaging resonated very well with the young population in Nigeria, who now called themselves *Obi-dient*. The movement soon gained attention on social media, canvassing for votes and defending their conviction in the movement. According to Oluwayemisi (2025), before Peter Obi emerged as the Labour Party candidate, many Nigerians had lost hope in Nigeria and its governance. However, when Mr Obi came into the picture as a third force, beyond the usual All Progressives Congress and the People's Democratic Party, there was a ray of hope. Many Nigerians, especially the youth, viewed Mr Obi as the only hope for rescuing the country from poor governance.

The *Obidient* movement consisted of people from various sectors of society, but it was primarily comprised of young people. Mokuye et al. (2023) categorise the *Obidient* movement group members into five. They are (1) professionals and intellectuals who were unhappy with how the country was governed. Such professionals regarded the country's status as being on the verge of collapse. (2) Celebrities with social media followers who endorsed Mr Obi and called on their followers to cast their votes for him. (3) Ethnic groups who saw Mr Obi's candidacy as essential to fulfilling the desire for a Nigerian president of Igbo extraction. (4) Another group of people are Nigerian activists who believed that there were many instances of human rights abuses in Nigeria, with particular reference to the #ENDSARS protests, especially the killing of Nigerians at Lekki Toll Gate. This group of *Obidients* viewed the 2023 general election as an opportunity to hold the government accountable for its human rights abuses. (5) The last group, according to Mokuye et al. (2023), consisted of Nigerians in the diaspora who required better leadership in Nigeria. This country of people believed they were abroad because of the bad leadership in Nigeria.

Lewis (2023) views Mr Peter Obi as the Messiah Nigerians have been waiting for. Lewis adds that Nigerians, tired of bad governance from the PDP and APC, believed Peter Obi was ready to offer the desperately needed leadership. As the political environment was charged, Mr Obi's opponents did not rest; they continued to counter him and engage his supporters. The PDP and the APC fought on one side, while Peter Obi fought on the other. As part of his efforts to galvanise his campaigns, Mr Obi significantly deployed social media platforms to educate voters and create awareness of his planned activities.

Social media are Internet-mediated communication platforms that allow users to share user-generated content (Agbo, 2024; Kwaghsster, 2024; Ogbuefi, 2024; Ogumba, 2024). These platforms enable users to serve as both senders and receivers of messages simultaneously, facilitating continuous interaction between senders and receivers. Examples of social media platforms that can be potentially used for political messaging include Facebook, WhatsApp, X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, and Instagram, among others. Social media platforms are popular in contemporary politics because they are the easiest and most convenient way to reach the populace. The masses are now on the Internet, as digital media platforms play a crucial role in how people spend their time. The political class has recognised these trends, and they rely on social media platforms to communicate their political messages to the voters. The masses, now also on social media platforms and political gladiators, have shifted their communication to these platforms.

In representative democracies, legitimacy is vested in the masses. This is because elected political officeholders derive their power from the voters who elect them to represent their interests in decision-making. Without the voters' support, it will be impossible for anyone to occupy a political office legitimately. The voters have the power to elect people into office during an election. According to Garnett (2019), voters are the beautiful brides in a democracy because those wishing to occupy political offices must gain their trust so that they will willingly vote them into office. The approach in campaigning may differ based on the level of democratic maturity of each country. For example, developed democracies like the United States of America will have a different approach to campaigning than nascent democracies like Nigeria.

In Nigeria, campaign seasons typically witness intense activities characterised by political alignments, realignments, political events, and other initiatives aimed at gaining a political advantage. Politicians and their supporters mobilise their arsenals to ensure they outsmart their opponents and get elected. Such was the case during the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria. In that election, there was an intensity from the younger Nigerian voters who invested their interest in the electoral process. According to Okpala (2024), the 2023 general elections in Nigeria generated significant attention from the Nigerian public and significantly charged the political atmosphere. Okpala adds that as a result of the campaign's intensity, extensive social media use occurred for political mobilisation.

Previous studies have examined the impact of social media on political communication. For example, Gever and Okoro (2020) conducted a study that combined content analysis and a survey and reported that users' self-presentation tactics influence their responses to persuasive messages on Facebook. The study of Gever and Okoro highlights the usefulness of social media in politicking but does not focus on a particular political movement. Wogu et al. (2019) examined the influence of social media political messages on citizens' perception of political parties, politicians and the government. The researchers reported that social media messages play a crucial role in influencing voter perceptions of political actors in contemporary Nigeria. Ugwuanyi et al. (2019) conducted a study and reported that social media platforms have become fertile grounds for people to express their views through visual content.

The use of social media for political movements has also been examined in the literature. Sorour and Lal (2014) conducted a study and reported that social media platforms have become at the centre of political activism, especially in developing countries. Sorour and Lal (2014) say that the instances of the use of social media for movements like mass protests at Tahrir Square in Cairo and Taksim Square in Istanbul, Turkey, demonstrations against sexual harassment in Delhi, India and the Shahbag Square uprising in Dhaka, Bangladesh all point to the usefulness of social media for promoting social and political movements. Hwang and Kim (2015) conducted a study to examine the influence of social media use on the intention to participate in social movements. The researchers examined a sample of 2,302 youth in South Korea. The researchers used a descriptive survey and reported that social media use played a significant role in influencing both the intention to participate in a social movement and actual participation. Sandoval-Almazan et al. (2014) conducted a study examining three social and political movements in Mexico over 20 years and reported that social media are practical tools for promoting political movements. Overall, the studies reviewed above point to the fact that social media are essential for fostering political movements. However, as political events continue to evolve, recent information is needed to understand the contributing role of social media platforms in promoting different political movements. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the role of social media in promoting the *Obidient* movement during Nigeria's 2023 presidential election.

Theoretical framework and research questions

This study employed a model of political movements utilising social media, as proposed by Sandoval-Almazan et al. (2014). The researcher suggested the model after evaluating the three political movements in Mexico. The model outlines four distinct stages that occur during the use of social media for promoting political movements. The stages are trigger event, traditional media response, viral organisation, and physical response. A trigger event is defined in the model as the incidence that propels a political movement. According to Sandoval-Almazan et al. (2014), information flow is usually intense in times of political events or social disruptions. As a result, discussions on social media platforms spread easily and quickly. The trigger event is that extraordinary event that unites people towards a political movement. The traditional media response is the second dimension in the use of social media for political movements, which refers to how traditional media outlets, such as radio, television, newspapers, and magazines, respond to a trigger event. The model suggests that information from conventional media serves as a crucial source of information for activists to advance their political movements. The third stage is viral organisation. This is the stage where people start building online communities after a mass reaction occurs. At this point, social media platforms are utilised to create groups and establish methods for promoting the political movement. Viral organization can lead to online and offline mobilisation. The last dimension of the model is physical reaction. This is the time when online mobilisation and other activities done with social media platforms lead to physical responses. The physical reaction could take the form of meetings, rallies, demonstrations, workshops, and other physical activities aimed at promoting the political movement. This study tested three of the four dimensions of the model. They include trigger events, viral organisation and physical reactions. Based on this, the study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What was the trigger event(s) for the *Obidient* political movement in Nigeria during the 2023 presidential election?

2. How were social media platforms used to organise the *Obidient* political movement during Nigeria's 2023 presidential election?
3. To what extent were social media platforms used for physical activities for the *Obidient* movement during Nigeria's 2023 general elections in Nigeria?

Methodology

Study design: An online survey research design was employed for this study. Gever (2024) reported in a study that most participants prefer online venues for participating in research. Therefore, an online survey was used to allow participants to participate in the study at their convenience.

Target Population: The target population of this study was all the *Obidient* movement on social media. Unfortunately, there are no official records of the total number of *Obidient* movement in Nigeria.

Sample size/Sampling technique: The study sample consisted of 385 *Obidient* movements in Nigeria. The researchers used an online calculator to determine the sample size, with a 95% confidence level, an error margin of 0.05, and a population proportion of 50%. The calculation yielded 385 as the sample size. The sampling technique was respondent-driven chain referral sampling. This form of sampling involves first recruiting the initial respondents, who then recruit subsequent respondents. The initial respondents were recruited through social media announcements that were posted on Facebook. They then recommended additional participants, and the process continued until all participants had been sampled.

Instrument for data collection: A structured questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The researchers used the questionnaire because it is capable of collecting data in large quantities. The questionnaire has a combination of multiple options and a four-point Likert scale. Three communication experts from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, tested the validity of the instrument. The researchers determined the reliability of the instrument using a test-retest with a two-week interval. The respondents in the reliability test were 20, and they did not take part in the actual study. The result showed a correlation coefficient of 0.76, showing that the instrument was reliable.

Method of data analysis: The analysis in this study was done using percentages, mean and standard deviation. The results were presented in tables. All analyses were conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0.

Results and Discussion

Among the 385 completed questionnaires, 365 were found to be correctly filled out and deemed valuable. This represents 96%, and the researchers considered this sufficient for data analysis. The study's results showed that the sample consisted of 53% males and 47% females. Additionally, the mean age of the sample was 25 years (range: 18-31 years), indicating that the majority of the respondents were young. Additionally, the majority (95%) of respondents indicated that they use social media daily. The most used social media platforms for movement were WhatsApp, X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, and YouTube. The result of the study is further presented based on the objectives of the study thus:

Table 1: The trigger event(s) for the *Obidient* political movement in Nigeria during the 2023 presidential election

S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	The desire for a Nigerian president of Igbo extraction	3.0	.09	Accepted
2	Mr Obi's promises	3.1	.98	Accepted
3	Obi's defection from the PDP as a result of bad treatment	3.2	.67	Accepted
4	The Muslim/Muslim ticket of the APC	3.0	.76	Accepted
5	Federal government's handling of the ENDSAR protests	3.0	.65	Accepted
6	Prolonged 2022 ASUU strike	2.9	.87	Accepted
7	The emergence of Alhaji Atiku Abubakar, another Northerner as a PDP presidential candidate	2.9	.89	Accepted
8	Concerns about the health of the APC presidential candidate	3.0	.76	Accepted
9	Endorsement of Mr Obi by some groups and individuals	2.7	.56	Accepted

In Table 1, the researchers examined the trigger event (s) that led to the use of social media for *Obidient* movement during Nigeria's 2023 presidential election. The study's results revealed that rather than a single trigger event, a series of events drove the use of social media in the political movement. This means that it was not just one event; instead, many events triggered the movement. This result has been extended to Sandoval-Almazan et al. (2014), who suggested that a trigger is typically responsible for the use of social media in political movements. In this study, we have demonstrated that multiple events can be triggered rather than a single event. This is particularly true because the movement was composed of different individuals who joined it at various stages. The implication is that other people had different triggers. The political movement started slowly and continued to grow as political events intensified.

Table 2: How social media platforms were used to organise the *Obidient* political movement during Nigeria's 2023 presidential election

S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Engagement with Mr Obi's social media posts	3.2	.78	Accepted
2	Posting of Mr Obi's activities on social media	2.8	.07	Accepted
3	Trying to convince other people through social media why Mr Obi was the best	3.0	.54	Accepted
4	Sharing Mr Obi's previous records on social media	3.1	.45	Accepted
5	Sharing information on the weaknesses of other candidates	3.2	.89	Accepted
6	Pointing out instances of bad governance in Nigeria	3.0	.78	Accepted
7	Creation of group social media platforms	3.1	.89	Accepted

The result of the study, as shown in Table 2, revealed how supporters of the *Obidient* movement used social media to promote the political movement. The study's results showed that the participants accepted all seven items as ways they utilised social media to promote the political

movement. All the items had mean scores of 2.5 and above, which was the benchmark for accepting or rejecting items. This study builds upon that of Oluwayemisi (2025), who examined the Obedient political movement but did not investigate how social media platforms were utilized to promote it. This additional information could be helpful in understanding the role of social media in political engagement.

Figure 1: The extent social media platforms were used to organize physical events

The result of the study, as shown in Figure 1, revealed the extent to which social media platforms were used to organise physical events during the Obedient movement in Nigeria. The study's results revealed that the majority of participants reported using social media platforms to a large extent. Although there was an option for not using social media, no participant reported that it was not used. This result has extended the study of Gever and Okoro (2020), who examined social media within the context of political communication but paid less attention to the issue of political movement. Wogu et al. (2019) also examined the impact of digital media on political communication, but they did not specifically investigate political movements. On the other hand, this study confirms the findings of Sandoval-Almazan et al. (2014), who reported that social media can be used for political movements, relying on social media to organise physical events.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the result of this study, the researcher concludes that social media platforms were used for political movements during Nigeria's 2023 presidential election. The researchers also conclude that the Obedient movement relied on social media to promote its activities. The group combined both online and offline activities to promote its ideas. Another conclusion of this study is that, rather than a single event, several events triggered the political movement during Nigeria's 2023 presidential election. This study has theoretical, practical and scholarly contributions.

Theoretically, the study has provided empirical data that could be useful for theorising social media use for political movements in developing countries like Nigeria. In practical terms, the study provides empirical data that can be useful in explaining how social media supports political movements. Scholarly, this study has enriched debates on the usefulness of social media in politicking. Despite the contribution of this study, it has some limitations. First, the researchers did not investigate the role of gender in the participants' responses. Additionally, the education level of the participants was not correlated with their responses. Finally, the contributing role of voting experience (first-time vs experienced voters) was not explored. Future studies are required to explore these limitations.

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